

Condition of Iodic Acid and Iodates in Aqueous Solution.

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The ease with which iodic acid becomes converted into iodine pentoxide and the formation of acid salts of iodic acid led J. Thomsen to state in 1874 that "it seems in the highest degree probable that iodic acid is dibasic with the molecular formula $H_2I_2O_6$."

The measurements of freezing point lowering, elevation of boiling points and electrical conductivity carried on by Rosenheim and Liebknecht (*Annalen*, 1899, **308**, 40) and Groschuff (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, **47**, 33) shows that solutions of iodic acid contain $H_2I_2O_6$.

In a previous paper (Dhar, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 585) it was pointed out that the precipitation values of iodate ion from iodic acid or from iodates of sodium and potassium on ferric hydroxide sol are comparable with those of divalent ions. Moreover, Bhagwat and Dhar (*ibid.*, 1929, **6**, 781) concluded from their experiments that coagulating power of iodate ion is of the same order as that of a bivalent ion on ceric hydroxide, zirconium hydroxide and ferric hydroxide sols. The recent work of Nayar and Gairola (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, **220**, 163) on the freezing point lowering and molecular conductivity difference is in favour of partial polymerisation of iodic acid and iodates.

From our experiments on the coagulation of chromium hydroxide, thorium hydroxide and beryllium hydroxide sols the following results are obtained.

TABLE I.

Chromium hydroxide sol.

		Dialysed soil I.	Dialysed soil II.
Concentration	...	109 g. of Cr_2O_3 per litre	127 g. of Cr_2O_3 per litre.
Amount of chloride	...	32.8 g. per litre	19.8 g. per litre
Purity	...	0.774	1.496
Ppt. conc. of KIO_3	...	0.0125M	0.0075M
Ppt. conc. of K_2SO_4	...	0.0088M	0.0055M

TABLE II.

Beryllium hydroxide sol.

Conc.	36.03 g./litre.
Amt. of chloride	35.14 g./litre
Purity	1.44
Ppt. conc. of KIO_3	0.00325M
Ppt. conc. of K_2SO_4	0.00325M

TABLE III.

Thorium hydroxide sol.

		Dialysed sol I.	Dialysed sol II.
Conc.		11.52 g. of ThO_2 per litre	11.94 g. of ThO_2 per litre
Amt. of nitrate		0.133 g./litre	0.0645 g./litre
Purity		20.26	43.25
Ppt. conc. of KCl		0.054M	0.038M
Ppt. conc. of KIO_3		0.0013M	0.00125M
Ppt. conc. of HIO_3		0.0029M	0.004M
Ppt. conc. of K_2SO_4		0.00036M	0.00026M

In order to observe whether potassium iodate in aqueous solution contains $\text{I}_2\text{O}''_6$ ions, the molecular conductivities of KCl and KIO_3 were compared under identical conditions at 20° . The following results are obtained.

TABLE IV.

Dilutions	...	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Mol. conductivity. of KCl		105.6	109.4	111.0	113.0	114.6	115.6	117.4	118.1	119.0
Mol. conductivity. of KIO_3		72.8	77.8	81.75	84.9	87.4	88.7	89.6	90.2	90.3

Recently the Raman spectra of iodic acid and alkaline iodates as solids and aqueous solutions have been investigated but no definite conclusions regarding polymerisation of iodic acid and iodates in aqueous solutions can be drawn from the Raman spectra. Nayar and Sharma (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, **220**, 169) have attributed the band at 634 and 334 to the polymers of iodic acid. But Venkateswaran (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, **2**, 119) does not agree with the above authors and advances the view that the line at 823 which is prominent as the component to the band at 779 is due to $\text{I}_2\text{O}''_6$ ions. Unfortunately this band which is present in solid potassium acid iodate only, cannot be detected in solutions of iodic acid, acid iodates and normal iodates, which from chemical evidence appear to be partially polymerised even in aqueous solutions. Hence it can be concluded that the coagulating power of solutions of iodic acid and iodates on positively charged hydroxide sols and the greater

difference in the molecular conductivities of potassium iodate at dilutions of 1024 and 4 in comparison with potassium chloride are the best evidence supporting the partial polymerisation of iodates and iodic acid in aqueous solutions.

SUMMARY.

1. The coagulating power of aqueous solutions of iodic acid and potassium iodate on the positively charged sols of beryllium hydroxide, chromium hydroxide and thorium hydroxide is much greater than that of potassium chloride and is comparable with potassium salts of dibasic acids.

2. The difference in the molecular conductivities of potassium iodate at dilutions 1024 and 4 is much greater than that of potassium chloride under the same conditions. These results support the view that in aqueous solution iodic acid and iodates are partially polymerised.

3. Evidence of polymerisation of iodic acid and iodates from Raman spectra seems inconclusive.

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